

ASPECTS OF SUICIDAL BEHAVIOR IN PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Imonova Maftuna

Termiz State Pedagogy teacher of the institute

ABSTRACT This article describes the manifestations of destructive personality behavior, types of character accentuation and factors of their formation.

Keywords: family, family relationships, destruction, destructive behavior, suitsid, destruction of family relationships, cognitive psychotherapy.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, another scientific direction of suicidology has been developed, in connection with sociology, psychology, medicine (medicine) psychiatry, the reasons for people's interest in doing this work, their personal characteristics, and how to live in them, that is, to live examines the hindering factors. In psychology, the term suicide was introduced for the first time by the Italian psychologist G. Deze in 1947, and it means "an act with the intention of taking one's own life", and there has always been interest in this issue. If the problem of suicide and assassination becomes a global problem every year, suicide attempts remain the attempts of a person to escape from one or another crisis situation in life. Suicidal act is characterized by the conscious desire of a person to sacrifice himself. Any purpose - death, motive (reason) - voluntarily leaving life to change psychic injuries, i.e. to make it one-sided.

Suicide is considered a solution to the accumulated psychological crisis. Suicide is an attempt to sacrifice one's own life, both internally and externally active. If internal active suicidal behavior is diagnosed earlier, the plan may not be carried out through disgust. Internal suicidal actions are manifested as follows. Internal experiences are caused by not being able to find a solution to the problem after some complicated conflicting situations or mental trauma, not understanding the value of one's life, they are in the following form: "You are not

alive, but you are (exist), "There is no happy life, etc. His ideas about life are characterized by pessimistic denial of the value of life.

Saint Augustine was the first to condemn suicide in the IV century. He considers suicide to be a form of murder that violates religious teachings. St. Augustine, justifying the society's view of suicide as a crime, cited four arguments, that is, the basis: - a guilty person does not have human rights (he cannot die as a guilty person without guilt); - a suicide bomber kills a person while taking his own life; - a pure soul overcomes all sufferings; - who committed suicide, will die as the worst of sinners. Suicidal behavior is a form of universal human reactions, including all forms of suicidal activity as a variant, the attitude of an individual to all options of possible death based on personal actions, and the following belong to them: - suicidal thoughts (passive - imagination, one's own imagination (fantasy) on the subject of limi, direct confession about death in an active - voluntary way); - suicidal intention - an active form of suicidal manifestation, that is, a tendency to commit suicide, its deepening is manifested in accordance with the level of development of the plan for its implementation, considering the method, time and place of suicide. will be - suicidal goals - following the decision of the volitional component; - suicidal attempts - purposeful suicide attempt that did not end in death; - suicides (visual, affective and real).

In the area where the suicide was committed, "Werther's Law" develops on the basis of rumors, which creates the basis for the repetition of the assassination. All deviant, destructive behavior is subject to Werther's Law (Imitate Me Law). Therefore, it is necessary to organize preventive measures immediately in the area where the assassination took place, to carry out educational work among the population (with the exception of minors), and to shed light on the psychophysiological mechanisms of suicide. Through these measures, we can prevent the spread of rumours, which means we can create a basis for the reduction of assassinations.

A state of stress (nervousness, strong excitement) is a dangerous mental and physiological strain, which inhibits all existing mental processes in a person. That is, a person in a state of stress hears poorly, does not see well, his sensitivity is

weakened, he does not fully understand the result of his actions, he falls into an incomprehensible depressed state of mind. Suicidal ideation: thoughts are added to the impulsive component and motivate the person to do the act. The period of suicidal thoughts and attempts is called the presuicide period, depending on whether it lasts for minutes (acute presuicide) or months. (chronic pesuicide) is distinguished. In acute pre-suicidal cases, sudden suicidal actions and tendencies are observed quickly without any stages. Overt signs of suicide include: Attempts to commit suicide are actions that do not end in death, but are aimed at taking one's own life. The act of suicide is the end of the imagination of the unsustainable in this situation - the end of suicide - the act that leads to the destruction of a person.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It is possible to determine the manifestation of individual-personal characteristics that are unconscious and not subject to perception in a person with the help of projective methods. In particular, in test methods such as "Human Image", "House-Tree-Human", "Non-Existent Animal", the total movements manipulated with the neck are a serious factor in suicide. According to A.G. Ambrumova, O.E. Kalashnikova, suicide victims often choose the purple color in the first position based on the color test "Method of Color Choices", which is related to the uniqueness of a person's individuality, views, interests and actions. reflects the difficulties of social adaptation. The preference for purple in the selection process indicates the relative lability of affect, representing the priority of mental stress, guilt, obedience and hope. According to D.D. Fedotov and his co-authors, suicidal attempts and desires (in the form of hysterical reactions) in adolescents, chronic verbal discrimination, disapproval of their opinion by relatives, limitation of independence, alcohol abuse and other drug use, at this age arise in relation to conflict situations related to inherent sexual problems.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In studies devoted to the study of adolescent suicide, we see that the behavior and

symptoms of suicide, and somatic changes of those who have committed suicide have been analyzed. For example, in the studies of B.M. Umarov, the main motive of suicidal behavior in pre-puberty and early puberty is considered to be conflicting experiences (6.9 percent, 30.7 percent) mainly related to mental illness and fear. and in post-puberty age, it was found that personal, family, teacher-student conflicts (39.2 percent, 44.9 percent) as well as conflicts related to social moral norms. Information about the subconscious actions of a person can be obtained by studying the characteristics of letters left by suicide victims before death. According to M.J. Sedein, their common feature is that they occupy the entire width of the text sheet, the side lines are small or non-existent, and the lines are not separated from each other. It is defined by the uniformity of the signature, the parallelism of the core, the hardness of the pressure, and stability. These characteristics correspond to sensory perception, which, unlike intuitive perception, is characterized by present awareness of the visible world.

A high level of anxiety was found in individuals with a tendency to suicide according to the "MMPI" and Spielberger-Hanin "self-assessment scale" methods. Information on various methods and means of suicide, as well as rites of suicide on Internet sites, is directly becoming a motivating factor for a teenager in a state of crisis to commit suicide. In practice, suicidal acts resulting from abuse and humiliation of a teenager through mobile phones and the Internet are also recorded. The fact that such negative factors are of high importance for teenagers, it is a social necessity to include them in the plan of psycho-prophylactic measures conducted among them. Knowing the psychological and social aspects that lead to suicide, the correct organization of preventive and preventative measures in this direction (from the Latin "praevenire" - prevention) will help to prevent it. Suicide does not happen suddenly: suicidal students warn others of their intentions very openly and leave plenty of time to take appropriate measures. Do not isolate the person in situations where the risk of suicide is high. Try to stay with him until the danger is over. Contact the experts. Suicidal people are not able to solve their problems. Doctor's help is very important. Tranquilizers, anti-depressants can be prescribed. The help of a psychologist is invaluable. Psychologists are able to

understand the most sensitive feelings and experiences of a person, to understand his observations and disturbing thoughts. The period of rehabilitation after suicide requires very careful attention. A suicide victim should be under supervision until he is fully rehabilitated

CONCLUSION

The existing psychological prevention in modern psychology is based on practical and scientific theories, and in the laws of the updated Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, educational institutions, family, mass media, community and law-enforcement organizations are implemented in cooperation. In psychological studies, it has not been fully determined which wrong educational influence or deviant behavior caused the suicide attempt. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a complex of pedagogical and psychological correctional programs for groups at risk of developing suicidal activity. These programs are aimed at determining the pedagogical and psychological methods and means of helping adolescent suicides to control their behavior, restoring and developing their connection with an alternative social environment. Psycho-prophylactic measures are aimed at providing psychological-pedagogical and social support in order to protect adolescents from the negative effects of the people around them, i.e.: a) family, neighborhood, educational group, class and pedagogical team, mass media ; b) consists in optimizing the conditions of education and upbringing affecting the main aspects of interpersonal relations of teenagers.

Therefore, the main goal of psychoprophylaxis is to identify negative social-psychological and pedagogical factors that lead to suicide attempts in adolescents and to implement corrective educational measures to eliminate them. Special prevention of adolescent suicide attempts includes: - dispelling rumors about suicidal problems; - research of social and psychological situations causing suicidal activity of teenagers; - to carry out correctional educational work with adolescents with a high level of suicidal risk, to establish constant communication with them, to discuss problems in cooperation; - Editing of mass media sources that are likely to cause suicidal thoughts: - National traditions, customs, rituals, interesting, entertaining programs are included in the plans of psycho-prophylactic

activities with teenagers with suicidal behavior, people around them. establishment of social relations with, allows to eliminate situations of social maladjustment that can lead to suicidal activity.

REFERENCES

1. Кернер Ф. «Стресс и ваше сердце». М. 2001.-С 138
2. Китаев-Смык Л.А. «Психология стресса». М. 1983. – С. 243
3. Китов А.И. «Психология управление». М. 1979. – С.67.
4. Короленко П. «Психофизиологическая адаптация к экстремальным условиям». Харьков. 1998. – С.142.
5. Ломов Б.Ф. «Соотношение социального и биологического как методологическая проблема психологии–Вопросы философии, 1976, № 4 –С.24.
6. Akhmedov, B. T. (2021). THE ROLE OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN STRENGTHENING FAMILY RELATIONS. In *WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS* (pp. 277-279).
7. Akhmedov, B. T. (2021). The Family as the Basic Unit. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(12), 201-204.
8. Иманова, М. Б. (2021). ШАХС ХАРАКТЕРИ АКЦЕНТУАЦИЯСИ ВА ДЕСТРУКТИВ ХУЛҚ-АТВОР. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(11), 1399-1403.
9. М.Б.Имонова СУИЦИДАЛ ХУЛҚ-АТВОР АКЦЕНТУАЦИЯСИ МУАММОСИ СИФАТИДА, *Международный современный научно-практический журнал НАУЧНИЙ ИМПУЛЬС № 4(100), часть 4 ноябрь, 2022 735-739 б.*
10. М.Б.Имонова ХАРАКТЕР АКЦЕНТУАЦИЯСИНИНГ ДЕСТРУКТИВ ХУЛҚ ШАКЛЛАНИШИГА ОИЛАНИНГ ТАЪСИРИ, *Муғаллим хем узликсиз билимлендириў № 6/7 – 2022 79-81 б.*
11. Imonova, M. B. (2023). MUSIQANING INSON HISSIYOTIGA TASIRI. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 2(3), 156-161.
12. Ashurova, S. F., & qizi Karimova, M. N. (2023). OILADA O ‘SMIRLARNING SOG ‘LOM TURMUSH TARZI VA OILAVIY HAYOT HAQIDAGI TASAVVURLARI SHAKLLANISHINING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 363-368.
13. Karimova, M. (2023). QIZLARNING MUHABBAT BORASIDAGI TASAVVURLARINING OILA MUSTANKAMLIGIGA TA’SIRI. *Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании*, 3(2).
14. Karimova, M. N., & Ashurova, S. F. (2023). PROFESSIONAL TA’LIMDA TAHSIL OLAYOTGAN QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASH VA ULARDA SOG ‘LOM TURMUSH TARZINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 369-373.
15. Imonova, M. B. (2023). Oila tinchligi–jamiyat faravonligi asosi. *Finland academic research science publisher*, 1148-1151.
16. То‘раxonova, M. A. (2023). BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARNING KASBIY

FAOLIYATIGA MOSLASHUVINI O‘ZIGA XOS PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(4), 1254-1257.

17. To‘raxonova, M. A. (2023). BO ‘LAJAK O ‘QITUVCHILAR SHAXSIY XISLATLARINING KASBIY TAYYORGARLIK JARAYONIDA SHAKILLANISHI *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3), 640-643.

18. To‘raxonova, M. (2023). BO ‘LAJAK O ‘QITUVCHILARNING KASBIY O ‘ZLIGINI ANGLASHINING PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARI. *Журнал Педагогики и психологии в современном образовании*, 3(3), 54-59.

19. Akhmedov, B. (2022). МУҲАББАТ ҲИСЛАРИ БОСҚИЧЛАРИНИНГ ГЕНДР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *Журнал Педагогики и психологии в современном образовании*, 2(6).

20. Akhmedov, B. T. (2022). МУҲАББАТ ҲИСЛАРИ БОСҚИЧЛАРИНИНГ ЖИНСГА БОҒЛИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *O‘ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(10), 87-92.

21. Akhmedov, B. T. (2021). The Family as the Basic Unit of Society. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(12), 201-204.

22. Akhmedov, B. (2022). Psychological characteristics of feelings of love.

23. Akhmedov, B. T. (2021). *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious*

24. Akhmedov, B. T. (2021). THE ROLE OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN STRENGTHENING FAMILY RELATIONS. In *WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS AND INNOVATIONS* (pp. 277-279).

25. Akhmedov, B. T. (2018). Игра система внедрения инновационных учебных программ. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (29), 17-19.

26. Akhmedov, B. T. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ СРЕДЫ НА ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СТЕРЕОТИПОВ В СЕМЕЙНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЯХ. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (1), 105-107.

27. Norbosheva, M. A. (2023). КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ МОТИВОВ УЧЕНИЯ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 255-258.

28. NORBOSHEVA, M. A. (2020). Отражение Национальных Ценностей В Национальных Играх. *ECLSS Online 2020b*, 312.

29. Narbasheva, M. A. (2021). Развитие компетентности у педагога дошкольных образовательных организаций. *Наука и образование сегодня*, (7 (66)), 65-66.

30. Norbosheva, M. (2022). PSIXOLOGIK MASLAXATDA MIJJOZ BILAN СУХБАТНИ БОШЛАШ ТЕХНИКАСИ ҲАҚИДА. *Журнал Педагогики и психологии в современном образовании*, 2(6).

31. Norbosheva, M. (2023). ИГРА КАК СРЕДСТВО ОВЛАДЕНИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЛИЧНОСТИ РЕБЕНКА. *Журнал Педагогики и психологии в современном образовании*, 3(2).

32. Narbasheva, M. A. (2021). The importance of pedagogical and psychological literacy of parents in preparing children for school education. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(1), 728-732.

33. Norbosheva M. A. Analysis of kid's psychological development through national games. – 2021.
34. Норбошева, М. (2023). Олий таълим тизимида таълим сифатини оширишда психологик билимдонликнинг ўрни. *Современные тенденции психологической службы в системе образования: теория и практика*, 1(1), 30-33.
35. Norbosheva, M. (2023). ИГРА КАК СРЕДСТВО ОВЛАДЕНИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЛИЧНОСТИ РЕБЕНКА. *Журнал Педагогике и психологии в современном образовании*, 3(2).
36. Норбошева, М. А. (2021). Мактабгача Ёшдаги Болаларнинг Оила Ҳақидаги Тасаввурларини Ўрганиш. *Инновации В Педагогике И Психологии*, 4(6).
37. Eshmurodov, O. (2023). ҚИЗЛАРНИ ОИЛАВИЙ ҲАЁТГА ТАЙЁРЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ ПСИХОЛОГИК ЖИХАТЛАРИ. *Журнал Педагогике и психологии в современном образовании*, (1). извлечено от <https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/9087>
38. Eshmurodov, O. (2023). SOG'LOM PSIXOLOGIK MUNIT OILA BARQARORLIGINING OMILI SIFATIDA . *Журнал Педагогике и психологии в современном образовании*, (1). извлечено от <https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/9088>
39. Eshmuradov, O., & Ismoilova, G. (2022). OILAVIY MUNOSABATLARDA BOLALAR TA'RBIYASIGA TA'SIRI ETUVCHI IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK OMILLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 201-205.
40. Eshmuradov, & G. Ismoilova (2022). OILAVIY MUNOSABATLARDA BOLALAR TA'RBIYASIGA TA'SIRI ETUVCHI IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK OMILLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B4), 201-205. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6902544
41. Eshmuradov Olmosbek Elamanovich (2021). OILA BARQARORLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISH OMILLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1 (4), 1318-1323.
42. М. А. Тилакова, & О. Э. Эшмуратов (2021). КРЕАТИВ КОБИЛИЯТЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИ. *Scientific progress*, 1 (6), 143-149.
43. Eshmurodov, O. (2022). ОИЛА МУСТАҲКАМЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-ПСИХОЛОГИК ОМИЛЛАРИ.
44. Abdullayeva, S., & Eshmuradov, O. (2023). ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЕ САМООПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ И ВЫБОР ПРОФЕССИИ УЧАЩИМИСЯ В ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ЗНАНИИ. *Журнал Педагогике и психологии в современном образовании*, 3(2). извлечено от

<https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/8395>

45. Jabborov, X., & Eshmuradov, O. (2023). ШАРҚ МУТАФАККИРЛАРИ ИШЛАРИДА МИЛЛИЙ ТАРБИЯ МАСАЛАСИ. Журнал Педагогикаси ва психологияси в современном образовании, 3(2). извлечено от

<https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/8394>

46. Eshmurodov, O., & Eshboyeva, B. (2023). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA JINSIY STERIOTIPLARNING YOSH XUSUSIYATLARI. Журнал Педагогикаси ва психологияси в современном образовании, 3(2). извлечено от

<https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/8388>

47. Eshmurodov, O., & Fazliddinova, U. (2023). OILADAGI IJTIMOIIY PSIXOLOGIK MUHITNING BARQARORLIGI TA‘MINLASHDA QAYNONA VA KELIN MUNOSABATLARINING O‘RNI . Журнал Педагогикаси ва психологияси в современном образовании, 3(1). извлечено от

<https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/8259>

48. Eshmurodov, O. (2023). OILAVIY MUNOSABATLAR BARQARORLASHSHUVIDA MILLIY QADRIYATLARNING ANAMIYATI. Журнал Педагогикаси ва психологияси в современном образовании, 3(1).

извлечено от <https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/8238>

49. Eshmurodov, O. (2022). ЎЗБЕК ОИЛАСИ МУСТАҲКАМЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДА МИЛЛИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ . Журнал Педагогикаси ва психологияси в современном образовании, 2(6). извлечено от

<https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/7449>

50. Eshmurodov, O. (2022). ҚАЙНОНА ВА КЕЛИН ЎРТАСИДАГИ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ БОЛАЛАР ТАРБИЯСИГА ТАЪСИРИ . Журнал Педагогикаси ва психологияси в современном образовании, 2(6). извлечено от

<https://ppmedu.jdpu.uz/index.php/ppmedu/article/view/7431>